

The Stochastic Finite Element Analysis of Natural Fiber Reinforced Composites with Large Variations in Geometrical and Mechanical Properties

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SUMMARY: A probabilistic analysis and design procedure for natural fiber reinforced composites with large variations in geometrical and mechanical properties was proposed by using the stochastic finite-element-based direct numerical simulation. In the present proposal, natural plant fibers are to be numerically modeled by finite element meshes, and then mechanical properties of the resulting composites are to be statistically evaluated by the Monte Carlo simulation. In addition to the present proposal of a numerical analysis, as one of the preliminary examples conducted by the authors, the natural plant (Kenaf) fiber unidirectionally reinforced plastic were statistically analyzed with several constituent material properties (fiber diameter, tensile modulus, and so forth) as their input random variables, and the statistics of mechanical properties (tensile modulus) of the composite were predicted from the estimated distributions of the output parameters. In this example, statistical data necessary for the simulation, such as mean, coefficient of variation, and probabilistic distribution, were obtained from the results of single-fiber tension tests. Further, the sensitivities evaluated from the correlation coefficients between all random input variables and a particular output variable were also examined. However in this preliminary example, some geometrical features unique to the plant fibers were not considered, such as irregular and cell-structural cross-sectional shapes and effects of ultimate plant cells, and full-fledged simulation examples based on more detailed three-dimensional finite element models for Kenaf fiber are going to be shown at another opportunity.

KEYWORDS: Natural Plant Fiber, Probabilistic Simulation, Statistical Experiment, Stochastic Finite Element Method, Monte Carlo Simulation

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has emerged a great deal of attention to so-called “green” composites, consisting only of the renewable and biodegradable natural resources such as plant fibers (as for reinforcing agents) and biodegradable polymers made from crops and garbage (as for binder/matrix resins) [1-3]. These kinds of composites are sustainable materials and will surely contribute to solve today’s environmental issues on the earth because they are first of all free from fossil fuels and as a consequence almost free from discharge of carbon dioxide and other harmful substances. In addition, the “green” composites are lightweight and can be cheap (depending on the price of the biodegradable polymers which will become cheaper as the demand for them gradually grows) compared to the conventional advanced composites and also may cultivate some new promising industries particularly in developing countries. It is regretted, however, that the natural plant fibers are, at least at the present moment, merely farm products, and therefore may suffer large scatter or variation as well as uncertainty in geometrical and material properties, originating in their biological nature and depending heavily on in what district and in what year the plants were grown and in what season and in what method they were harvested and subjected to fiber extraction operation. It is quite probable that this variation in geometrical and material properties of the fibers will lead to large variation in macroscopic mechanical properties of the resulting composites. Therefore there is a great deal of possibility that this variation in fiber properties, as well as composite forming technique, fiber/matrix interfacial strength, control of biodegradability, and thermal stability, can be one of the primary factors which determine the quality and the material/structural strength reliability of “green” composites, especially in the cases of their future applications to secondary or redundant structural components. These views on this environmentally-preferable composites stress the importance of careful and pertinent investigations on the mechanical properties of both the plant fibers themselves and the resulting plant fiber reinforced composites, from various angles, especially from statistical and biomechanical points of view.

Statistical investigations on mechanical properties of plant fibers have been made by several researchers. Kulkarni, *et al.* [4] statistically examined tensile strength of coir fibers (extracted from coconut husks) based on the classical two-parameter Weibull model. They reported that the large scatter observed in the fracture strengths of coir fibers and the strength distribution at any gauge length (and for any diameter of fiber) could be represented satisfactorily by unimodal Weibull distributions. They also reported that the double logarithmic plot of mean fracture strength against gauge length showed a kinked line, that is, a combination of a linear downward line with respect to the gauge length longer than 6 mm and a constant line for the length below 6 mm. They pointed out

the existence of two distinct length-dependent flaws governing the tensile strength of coir fibers. Although they could not clearly identify what those two distinct kinds of flaws actually are, at least they believed in the gross flaw of the order of 6 mm. Zhang *et al.* [5] developed the modified Weibull/weakest-link model by incorporating the “within-fiber”, in addition to the “among-fiber”, diameter variation, which, they said, was necessary for fibers with considerable geometrical irregularities, such as wool fibers, although, to the best knowledge of the authors, several negative observations have also been reported on this topic. Their new Weibull model (slightly modified from the well-known model by Watson and Smith [6]) requires diameter profile measurements over the whole gauge length in order to take account of the within-fiber diameter variations. In their study, this modified Weibull model was applied to the single-fiber tensile strengths of merino wool, and could explain the experimental data more precisely than the conventional Weibull model. Although they did not mention about applications of their model to other fibrous materials, it may be useful for the plant fibers as well because the present authors are observing the very severe geometrical irregularities not only on the cross sections but also along the gauge length for even intact plant (Kenaf) fibers, as will be shown later in this report. However it should be noted that even this modified Weibull model by Zhang *et al.* will not completely represent the aforementioned kinked line reported by Kulkarni *et al.* in the strength-length relations of plant fibers.

As can be seen in the previous relevant studies briefly mentioned above, plant fibers exhibit unique mechanical properties the existing statistical analysis models may not fully be able to describe. It will be easily realized that this limitation of existing models to the plant fibers is mainly due to the biological or biomechanical unique features they have in common. The plant fibers are actually a kind of composite themselves [7], which consist of several single plant cells packed in the cross section. The plant cell fibers (ultimate fibers) are glued together with non-cellulosic substances (pectin, hemicellulose, and lignin) to form the actual plant fiber. The length of the cell fibers and the number of them per cross section of the plant fibers vary from each species, each variety, and maybe even each individual and each portion. For instance, the present authors confirmed that Kenaf (*Hibiscus cannabinus L.*) has its bast fibers consisting of approximately 15 - 20 ultimate cell fibers, which are 2 - 3 mm long and 10 - 20 μm in diameter on average, and with a hole called “lumen” (Fig.1). The primary structural part of the ultimate cell fiber is the secondary cell wall which consists of cellulose microfibrils and hemicellulose matrix. The volume fraction of cellulose microfibrils and their orientation angle against the fiber axis in there dominate the mechanical properties of the cells themselves and consequently those of the entire plant fibers made of them. It should also be noted that the cellulose microfibril is said to be very sensitive to the environment stimulation and its

orientation angle can be easily changed by moisture, heat, or alkali treatments. Anyway, plant fibers are definitely not a homogeneous fiber with a uniform circular cross section just like their synthetic counterparts, and hence it is quite obvious that, without considering, more or less, this irregular, cell-structural feature of the plant fibers, their mechanical properties can not be captured properly.

Fig.1 cross sections of Kenaf fiber

Up to the present date, several attempts have been done to model the plant fibers in biomechanical manners. As one of the early attempts, McLaughlin and Tait [7] proposed the empirical equations of mean tensile strength and mean fracture strain in terms of cellulose content and microfibril angle for a wide variety of plant fibers. Yamamoto, *et al.* [8] introduced a mechanical cell model to describe the biomechanical properties of the wood fiber.

These previous studies cited above treated only the single cell (i.e. the single ultimate fiber). More recently, Inagaki, *et al.* [9] proposed the geometrical hexagonal model to evaluate the critical fiber length in the light of interfacial strength with and without alkali treatment for the bamboo fiber reinforced composite. Their hexagonal fiber model is a fiber bundle made up of a number of ultimate fiber cells and can give us more practical insights into the mechanical behavior of natural plant fibers. However these existing studies on biomechanical modelings of plant fibers are of theoretical (mathematical) modeling and therefore their applications will be limited to some extent in the context of practical material/structural analysis and design purposes. As the image of actual plant fiber's cross sections shown in Fig.1 implies, a numerical, stochastic modeling methodology, e.g., finite element analysis and probabilistic simulation, may be after all necessary so as to reasonably represent such kind of randomness of three-dimensional, multi-cellular plant fibers. In this report, the authors are going to employ an appropriate finite-element-based probabilistic simulation procedure which can be applied to plant fiber reinforced composites.

SIMULATION PROCEDURE

In this report, a probabilistic analysis and design system for natural fiber reinforced composites with large variations in geometrical and mechanical properties is proposed by using the stochastic finite-element-based direct numerical simulation. In the present proposal, natural plant fibers are to be

numerically modeled by finite element meshes, and then mechanical properties of the resulting composites are to be statistically evaluated by the Monte Carlo simulation. The general-purpose finite element analysis code ANSYS® version 6.1 was employed, which is equipped with fundamental simulation functionalities (typical probabilistic functions, Monte Carlo simulation loop, statistical post-processing, and so forth) for constructing a probabilistic analysis and design procedure for each particular problem such as the one dealt in this study [10]. This is very beneficial because this simulation template enables the authors to bypass the trivial portions of the program coding and to focus only on the essential parts of the stochastic finite element modeling.

The present probabilistic procedure executes the deterministic problem several times, each time with a different set of values for the random input variables, and hence the key tasks up to the point of simulation execution are, (a) to construct a complete set of deterministic finite element analysis in the form of batch files written in APDL (ANSYS Parametric Design Language: a kind of script language understandable by ANSYS program [10]), (b) to define geometrical or physical parameters, e.g. Young's modulus, diameter, loads, and so on, as "random input variables" and to specify their statistical information such as mean, standard deviation, and probabilistic distribution type, and finally (c) to select the resulting output parameters of interest, e.g. Young's modulus and strength of the composites. The deterministic finite element solution description written in APDL can be anything as long as it is consistent and closed by itself with proper definitions of the input random variables and the output parameters. The initial values for the random input variables can be set as their mean values, while those for the output parameters can be arbitrary. After the simulation loops, the statistical information on the output parameters is post-processed in according with the standard statistical style (i.e. basic statistic evaluations with a certain confidence limit, histogram plots, cumulative probability curve plots, correlation analysis, and so on). In addition, the sensitivities evaluated from the correlation coefficients between all random input variables and a particular output variable can be readily visualized.

SIMULATION EXAMPLE

In this section, a simple, preliminary example for the stochastic finite-element-based simulation of composites is shown. Kenaf fiber-reinforced plastic (Kenaf FRP) [11] is considered for the present example. The matrix polymer can be either the conventional or the biodegradable.

Kenaf harvest and acquisition of statistical fiber properties

In this study, the Kenaf fiber samples were obtained from the individual Kenaf plants (about 300 cm in height) which were grown, harvested and retted (for fiber extraction) by the authors last year

(Fig.3 (a) – (c)). The diameter profiles of the fibers were measured over the entire length of each sample at 100 μm interval by using an optical microscope with a calibrated eyepiece. The obtained diameter profiles show the severe geometrical irregularities along fiber length (Fig.4 (a) and (b)). After that, tensile properties of those natural fibers were obtained from the static single-fiber tensile tests (gauge length $L = 25$ mm, cross-head speed : 0.5 mm/min), and the mean values and the coefficient of variations of the geometrical and mechanical properties of Kenaf fibers were obtained (Table 1). In addition, for the purpose of determination of probabilistic distribution types for the fiber properties, in Fig.5 through Fig.7, histograms and probabilistic plots of diameter, tensile modulus, and tensile strength of the fibers are respectively made. From those probabilistic plots, the normal (Gaussian) distribution was adopted for distribution type of the fiber diameter, on the other hand Weibull distributions were adopted for both the tensile modulus and the tensile strength. From the slopes of regression lines for the probability plots, the Weibull scale parameters for the tensile modulus and the tensile strength were found to be, respectively, 2.32 and 1.77. Those experimental results are going to be used for the following probabilistic simulation for Kenaf FRP.

Fig.3 (a) Kenaf plants, (b) Kenaf fiber obtained, and (c) a microscopic image of the fiber

Fig.4 two typical cases of Kenaf fiber diameter profile along fiber length

Table 1 experimental measurement of Kenaf fiber (sample size $N = 270$)

fiber diameter d (μm) • CV % •	CV of diameter variation (%) • CV % •	Fiber tensile modulus E (GPa) • CV % •	Fiber tensile strength σ (MPa) • CV % •
123 (28.9%)	23.1 (35.3%)	17.4 (46.1%)	219.4 (59.1%)

CV : coefficient of variation (%)

(a)

(b)

Fig.5 fiber diameter histogram and probabilistic plot on normal distribution scale

(a)

(b)

Fig.6 fiber tensile modulus histogram and probabilistic plot on two-parameter Weibull distribution

Fig.7 fiber tensile strength histogram and probabilistic plot on two-parameter Weibull distribution

Probabilistic simulation: results and discussion

In the present example, statistical data for the input random parameters (elastic moduli of fiber and matrix, diameter and volume fraction of fiber, and so on) were set based on the aforementioned single-fiber tensile test results if available. Note that the data unavailable from the test results were guessed in as physically and phenomenologically reasonable ways as possible. In this preliminary example, all of the geometrical irregularities of Kenaf fibers both on cross section and along length were supposed to be included in the diameter variation only, and consequently the reinforcing plant fiber is assumed to be represented by a single homogenous solid fiber, diameter of which exhibits the large statistical scatter in accordance with the measurement. In Fig.8, the list of the input parameters used in the simulation and a typical finite element mesh generated during the simulation were shown. As the generated mesh in Fig.8 shows, there is not any necessity for finite element employment in this most simplified case. However the present authors believe that finite element modeling will play a key role in more detailed, full-fledged numerical simulations.

	mean	CV	distribution	shape param.	scale param.
Fiber	$E_L \cdot \text{GP} \cdot \cdot$	17.4	weibull	2.32	19.6
	$E_T \cdot \text{GP} \cdot \cdot$	1.74			1.96
	$G_{LT} \cdot \text{GP} \cdot \cdot$	3.3			3.7
	$G_{TT} \cdot \text{GP} \cdot \cdot$	0.67			0.76
	$d \text{ (}\mu\text{m)}$	123			28.9%
	$V_f \text{ (}\% \text{)}$	40	0%	constant	-
Matrix	$E \cdot \text{GP} \cdot \cdot$	0.5	5%	normal	-
	ν	0.3	0%	constant	-

Fig.8 the input random variables for the simulation and a typical finite element mesh generated during the simulation

In Table 2, the output parameters are provided which are the results after 30 Monte Carlo simulation loops, As can be seen, the scatter of the longitudinal modulus E_L is very large (44.1%) certainly reflecting the scattering nature of the reinforcing Kenaf fiber. This is supported by the sensitivity analysis result shown in Fig.9, which indicated the contribution of Kenaf fiber modulus (E_{f_L} : blue one in the circular chart) on the variation of the composite is 57 %.

Table 2 the output parameters, i.e. longitudinal and transverse elastic moduli (E_L and E_T), and shear moduli (G_{LT} and G_{TT}), obtained after 30 simulation loops

	mean	CV	
Composite	$E_L \cdot GP \cdot \cdot$	7.2	44.1%
	$E_T \cdot GP \cdot \cdot$	0.74	16.0%
	$G_{LT} \cdot GP \cdot \cdot$	0.29	16.1%
	$G_{TT} \cdot GP \cdot \cdot$	0.42	10.4%

Fig.9 sensitivity ratio of the random input parameters to the longitudinal elastic modulus (E_L) of the resulting composite

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, first, benefits and advantage of natural fiber reinforced “green” composites were briefly mentioned, and then importance of statistical and biomechanical numerical modeling of natural plant fibers for properly capturing the mechanical behaviors of this environmentally preferable composite was underlined. After that, a probabilistic analysis and design procedure for natural fiber reinforced composites with large variations in geometrical and mechanical properties was proposed by using the stochastic finite-element-based direct numerical simulation. From the preliminary example in the case of Kenaf FRP by using the most simplified finite element mesh, large variation of the mechanical properties of the resulting composite was numerically predicted. However in this preliminary example, some geometrical features of Kenaf fibers were not considered, such as irregular and cell-structural cross-sectional shapes and effects of ultimate cell fibers, and full-fledged simulation examples based on more detailed three-dimensional finite element models for Kenaf fiber should be shown as a next step.

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